

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lymph node metastasis: MMP9.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer. Metastasis to the lymph node (“regional” metastasis)
7 generally precedes distant metastasis, and we recently demonstrated that metastasis to the lymph nodes
8 is a likely prerequisite for metastasis to the central nervous system (CNS) in humans with breast cancer
9 (1-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the
10 primary tumor and in the lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer to define the lymph node
11 metastatic transcriptome. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and
12 up-regulation upon metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer, MMP9, as a candidate
13 therapeutic target for the medical management of lymph node metastasis.
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1 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
2 transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes
3 the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary
4 tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of
5 NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the
6 lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in
7 metastasis to the lymph nodes to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous
8 study of the lymph node metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is
9 up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize
10 efficacy: MMP9.

11 Results

12 **Figure 1:** MMP9 is differentially expressed in lymph node metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

13 I. Lymph node metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

14 $n=18$ primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

15 $n=16$ lymph node metastases from humans with breast cancer

16 ID	17 p-value	18 t	19 B	20 logFC	21 Gene	22 Rank	23 %DE
203936_s_at	1.80E-02	-2.4848401	-3.35567	-0.92704013	MMP9	863/22277	96.1

16 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in
17 lymph node metastases of humans with breast cancer in a second cohort (10), we validated differential
18 expression of matrix metalloproteinase 9, encoded by MMP9 in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans
19 with breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of MMP9 changed more than 95% of the human lymph
20 node metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this
21 case, 22,277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of MMP9
22 messenger RNA in lymph node metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of MMP9 during disease
23 progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

18 Thus, we concluded that differential and increased expression of MMP9 likely defined the lymph node
19 metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

20 Discussion

21 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
22 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
23 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of MMP9, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity
24 and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lymph node metastasis who have failed
25 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lymph node
26 metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or
27 those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A
28 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and
ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting
tumor clone resistance (11).

A description of basic chemotherapy approaches supported by our discovery research follows.

- 1 1. **Intensification of standard chemotherapy with MDR pump inhibition** at baseline and at
2 resistance
 - 3 a. The pump is the only entity considered at resistance for compensatory clinical inhibition.
- 4 2. **Multi-drug** approach targeting DNA replication and cell division: **EZH2, TK1, TYMS, AURKA, and TOP2A**
 - 5 a. Adjunctive option 1: Targeted kinase adjunctive
 - 6 b. Adjunctive option 2: Targeted phosphatase adjunctive
- 7 3. **A general solid tumor dual inhibitor** strategy: PARP1/2 inhibition together with CDK4/6
8 inhibition
- 9 4. Genomic medicine-based (tailored) **combinatorial phosphatase inhibition**.
 - 10 a. The number of phosphatases targeted in this approach will depend on tolerability and deliverability
11 of successful targeting combinations.
- 12 5. Genomic medicine-based (tailored) **combinatorial kinase inhibition**.
 - 13 a. The number of kinases targeted in this approach will depend on tolerability and deliverability of
14 successful targeting combinations
- 15 6. **A complete growth factor inhibition** strategy.
 - 16 a. Targeting angiogenesis through VEGF-A lies at the basis of this fifth chemotherapeutic strategy.
 - 17 b. The approach relies on **accurate and complete description of growth factors induced at the**
18 **80-99% range** of the transcriptome in order to completely restrict growth factor signaling
 - 19 c. **A reduced cytotoxic regimen** is ideally administered with the growth factor inhibitor cocktail to
20 induce cell death whilst activating starvation responses
 - 21 d. **Kinase targeting for compensatory inhibition**.
- 22 7. **Immunoglobulin-based therapeutic targeting: drug discovery approach**.
 - 23 a. This approach is agnostic to considerations or concepts that prevail in modern medical oncology
24 like cytotoxicity associated with standard chemotherapies like nitrogen mustard based agents, as
25 well as to considerations common when targeting general properties of the cancer cell, like those
26 considered by the multi-drug approach which aims to block DNA replication and cell division
 - 27 b. Instead, it utilizes intensive study of tumor transcriptomes for identification of disease-specific
28 therapeutic vulnerabilities for clinical intervention using targeted, designed monoclonal antibody
reagents.
 - c. Targets identified here, rather than being assembled into an immunoglobulin-based therapeutic
strategy, can be used as an individual agent as adjunctive treatments in other chemotherapeutic
approaches.
8. **Treatments that target the immune system** for control of disease (cancer).
 - a. Class I and II antigen presentation by the tumor through **UBE2L6** modulation
 - b. Natural killer cell tumor surveillance through **NKG7 and HLA-V together with KIR2DL3**
 - i. Gamma delta T cells may function with NK cells in this pathway.
 - c. **Targeting exhaustion** (“reinvigoration”) at the tumor microenvironment using pharmacologic
inhibition of **CTLA4 AND PD-1**, like involving cytotoxic immune responses by CD8 T lymphocytes
 - i. Novel immunoreceptor targeting TIGIT, LAG-3, VISTA and other surface receptors

- 1 9. **Rational responses to resistance.**
- 2 a. **CDKN re-activation** through CDK4/6 inhibitor escalation
- 3 b. CDKN re-activation through **UBE2C and UBE2S** modulation
- 4 10. Targeting **centers of activity** in the cancer cell.
- 5 a. **Kinetochores**
- 6 i. SPC24/SPC25, Nuf2, NDC80
- 7 ii. Other components of the kinetochore plate
- 8 b. **Cell membrane** during cytokinesis
- 9 i. PKC isoforms; ECT2.

18 **References**

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9 in human cancer.

10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 **Methods**

19 We utilized GSE57968 (9) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in
20 metastasis to the lymph nodes and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with
21 GSE44408 [10] for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and
22 R-based computational methods. When data for GSE44408 is not present, it failed to satisfy validation,
23 and was consulted but omitted.
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